

HYGROTHERMAL EFFECTS ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF T800/924C CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present work is to evaluate the response of the T800/924C carbon fibre-epoxy composite system (currently available for aerospace structural applications) in hot-wet environments. The weight gains, maximum moisture contents and diffusion coefficients of unidirectional and various multidirectional laminates immersed in boiling water (accelerated ageing) are reported. Data is also presented on the effects of moisture and temperature on the compressive strength/failure mode of unidirectional laminates and multidirectional plates with an open hole. It is observed that the failure in the hot-wet specimens always occurs as a result of out-of-plane microbuckling of the 0° plies. This is attributed to the reduction in matrix strength properties and weakening of the ply interface arising from elevated temperatures and environmental conditioning.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced plastics are increasingly being used in the manufacture of aircraft structural components and in order to certify these components for service use it is important to examine their mechanical behaviour under a range of environmental conditions. It is known that hot and humid environments can degrade some aspects of the material performance in particular the compressive strength [1,2]. Water absorption by the epoxy resin leads to a reduction in the glass transition temperature and to a softening of the resin with a loss of stiffness and strength which causes fibre microbuckling and premature laminate failure [3]. The degradation increases as the conditions become more severe. The quantity of water absorbed by a laminate is therefore of considerable importance, in particular to the designer when setting design limits for structures operating in moist environments.

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the water absorption of the T800/924C carbon fibre-epoxy system and determine its effect on the compressive strength of unidirectional and multidirectional laminates with an open hole. A computer program [4] is used for the calculation of the quantity of water absorbed by the composite laminates and the profile of the moisture distribution through the laminate thickness during exposure to boiled water (accelerated ageing). The numerical results are confirmed by experimental measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIALS AND TEST SPECIMENS

Laminates measuring 1000 mm x 300 mm were manufactured from T800/924C carbon fibre-epoxy prepreg supplied by Ciba-Geigy Plastics Company; the composite contained approximately 65% by volume fibres. The laminates were consolidated and cured in an autoclave at the Royal Aerospace Establishment (DRA-Farnborough), at a temperature of 170°C for 1 h and subsequently post-cured for 4 h at 190°C. Three different lay-ups were produced: a 16-ply unidirectional (ud) and two 24-ply multidirectional (md) laminates having a stacking sequence of $[(\pm 45/0_2)_3]_s$ and $[(90_2/0_2)_3]_s$. Immediately after manufacture, the laminates were cut into specimens measuring 110 mm x 10 mm for the unidirectional and 240 mm x 50 mm for the multidirectional, and stored in a desiccator to minimise moisture absorption prior to testing or environmental conditioning. A 5 mm diameter hole was drilled at the centre of each multidirectional specimen using a tungsten carbide bit; by drilling from both sides of the specimen using a 2 mm pilot hole, the break through occurred at about mid-thickness which generally prevented any splitting or delamination of the outer plies [1].

ENVIRONMENTAL EXPOSURE

In order to predict mathematically the content and distribution of moisture in a laminate it is necessary to know the equilibrium level M_∞ (i.e. the maximum amount of moisture that can be absorbed by a laminate at a given humidity) and the diffusion coefficient D . To measure these data normally requires exposure times of over six months, even for relatively thin laminates of say 1 mm thick [4]. In this work the conditioned specimens were immersed in boiling water so the equilibrium level was reached in a period of few weeks. During the conditioning the specimens were periodically removed from the environment and weighed using an electronic balance accurate to ± 0.0001 g. Their weight gain, expressed as a percentage of their dry weight, was plotted against square root time as illustrated in Figs. 1a and 1b; the slope of the linear part is used subsequently in the calculation of the diffusion coefficient. After the maximum moisture content reached the specimens were removed and weighed once more before being machined in readiness for through thickness slitting. Each specimen was sliced carefully all the way through to give six slices. By weighing, drying and reweighing each slice its percentage uptake of water was found and plotted against through thickness position to give the moisture distribution. Figs. 2a and 2b.

As stated above all specimens were initially stored in a desiccator to minimise moisture ingress. Those to be tested in the dry condition were loaded to failure within about 10 minutes of being removed from the desiccator and although it is acknowledged that some moisture absorption might have occurred, it is assumed that the moisture content in these specimens is negligible [1].

APPARATUS AND MECHANICAL TESTS

Unidirectional Specimens

Compression tests on the unidirectional specimens were performed following the procedures outlined in CRAG tests methods [5], using a modified Celanese test jig [6,7] at a constant compression rate of 0.017 mm s^{-1} on a screw-driven machine of load capacity 50 kN. The conventional serrated grip faces of the Celanese were replaced by spark eroded inserts to

Fig. 1. Comparison of experimental and Fickian moisture uptake against root time. a) T800/924C unidirectional laminate and b) T800/924C [(±45/0₂)₃]_s laminate

Fig.2. Comparison of experimental and Fickian through- thickness moisture distribution a) [0₈]_s and b) [(±45/0₂)₃]_s (both laminates immersed in boiling water).

eliminate adhesively bonded tabs on the specimen ends [7]; by having no tabs the entire surface of the specimen was exposed for water absorption.

In order to measure the compressive strength as a function of temperature and humidity, two extra inspection ports were drilled on the Celanese alignment sleeve, so a hot-air blower and a steam pipe could be attached. Symmetric airflow was achieved and the specimen was heated evenly. The temperature and humidity of the environment were monitored regularly by a thermocouple and a Testoterm hygrometer. It took less than 5 min to reach 100°C and the environmental conditioning chamber was capable of maintaining the temperature to within 3. The specimens were allowed to 'soak' for about 10 min before being tested. At least five tests were carried out per test condition, hot-dry (20°C-100°C) and hot-wet (20°C-100°C, 95% RH). Strain gauges were used on both faces of all specimens to be tested in hot-dry conditions to measure axial strain and monitor the degree of bending.

Multidirectional Specimens

The multidirectional notched specimens were tested under the same hot-dry and hot-wet conditions as the unidirectional specimens using a home-made environmental chamber in a servo-hydraulic test machine at a loading rate of 1 kN s⁻¹. The specimens were untabbed straight-sided and were loaded by shear action by means of wedge grips with a spark eroded surface finishing. They were of gauge section 120 mm x 50 mm, and were tested by using an anti-buckling device to prevent macrobuckling (Euler bending) during the test. The anti-buckling device increases the flexural stiffness of the composite plate but carries no load. Considerations of importance throughout the compressive test procedure were alignment of the specimen in the grips and proper attachment of the anti-buckling device to the specimen. Full details on the experimental technique have been documented previously by Soutis [8].

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results consist of moisture absorption measurements, and compressive strength/stiffness data for unidirectional and multidirectional notched laminates. The shear properties of the T800/924C system (measured by using the Iosipescu specimen) are also presented in order to understand how shear strength/stiffness affects the compressive behaviour.

MOISTURE ABSORPTION

In a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin, moisture is absorbed by the resin; the fibres do not absorb moisture. Most of the evidence in the literature suggests that water is absorbed by a bulk diffusion mechanism in the resin and for flat plates the rate of moisture absorption $\partial M / \partial t$ through the thickness direction (z) can be described by Fick's second law:

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 M}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

where D is known as the diffusion coefficient. It should be remembered that the two main characteristics of Fickian behaviour are: **i)** the absorption curve should be linear initially and **ii)** the moisture content should reach a saturation level (M_{∞}) at large values of time. The analytical solution of Eqn (1) yields the amount of moisture uptake which varies with time as [9]

$$M(t) = M_o + (M_\infty - M_o) \frac{4}{h} \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{\pi}} \quad (2)$$

where M_o is the initial amount of moisture in the solid, M_∞ is the final amount at equilibrium and h is the laminate thickness. From Eqn (2) it is clear why the initial part of the plot of $M(t)$ versus the square root of time should be a straight line. The diffusivity can be now determined using the value of M for two different values of time:

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4(M_\infty - M_o)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M(t_2) - M(t_1)}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Eqn (3) is often considered with $M_o=0$. The diffusivity can now be determined by using Eqn (3) and the slope of Figs. 1a and 1b for the unidirectional and $[(\pm 45/0_2)_3]_s$ multidirectional laminate, respectively.

The slope M / \sqrt{t} is obtained from using the complete specimen (finite plate) and therefore includes moisture diffused through all six surfaces. This gives a greater slope than would have been obtained for an infinite plane sheet as moisture had diffused through six sides instead of two. To give a better estimate of the true one-dimensional coefficient D_∞ a correction factor given by Shen and Springer [10] is used:

$$D_\infty = D \left(1 + \frac{h}{W} + \frac{h}{\ell} \right)^{-2} \quad (4)$$

where w and ℓ are the specimen width and length, respectively. The numerical results for D and D_∞ are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Coefficient of moisture diffusion for T800/924C laminates

Diffusivity mm ² /s	$[0_8]_s$	$[(\pm 45/0_2)_3]_s$
D	1.2×10^{-6}	1.1×10^{-6}
D_∞	5.66×10^{-7}	8.18×10^{-7}

The diffusivity of the multidirectional laminate is about 30% higher than that of the unidirectional laminate, probably due to more entrances available for the water to diffuse through the plate and due to larger interfacial absorption of the 45° plies [11]. The diffusion coefficient and the equilibrium moisture content ($M_\infty = 1.42\%$) are used with the computer program developed in [4] to estimate the through thickness moisture distribution, Figs. 2a and 2b. It is clear that although Fickian diffusion does not exactly model the actual diffusion, it is sufficiently accurate for the cases examined.

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

Strength Data and Failure Modes

The effect of temperature and environmental conditioning on the compressive strength/stiffness of the T800/924C unidirectional laminate is presented in Table 2; shear strength properties are also given. It can be seen that moisture and high temperature has a marked influence on the

composite's compressive behaviour. At operating temperature of 100°C-dry the strength has been reduced by more than 30% and the failure strain has dropped from 0.96% to 0.73% (approximately 24% reduction). This is because the stiffness of the epoxy resin is reduced substantially with increasing temperature; the shear modulus has been reduced by almost 20%, Table 2. In uniaxial compression reduction in matrix modulus means reduced support for the fibres, which promotes premature failure of the composite by out-of-plane fibre microbuckling. The compressive strength is further reduced (by 54%) when the laminate contains 1.4% by weight moisture and tested at 100°C and 95% RH. It can be seen from the results shown in Table 2, that the compressive strength (σ_c) is only 20% of the elastic shear modulus; remember that Rosen's analysis of fibre buckling predicts that σ_c is equal to the shear modulus. This suggests that a plastic-buckling analysis is required in order to estimate strength more accurately. The results quoted in Table 2 are based on the average of five specimens tested at each environmental condition; the coefficient of variation is less than 5%.

Table 2. Compressive strength properties of T800/924C unidirectional laminates

Test Temperature °C	Compressive Strength MPa	Young's Modulus GPa	Shear Strength MPa	Shear Modulus GPa
20-dry	1415	160	110	6.0
20-wet	1060	-	-	-
50-dry	1230	155	105	5.8
50-wet	930	-	-	-
80-dry	1137	149	98	5.4
80-wet	828	-	-	-
100-dry	973	136	90	4.9
100-wet	654	-	-	-

* Secant modulus measured at 0.25% axial strain.

Failure of the room temperature specimens was sudden and occurred mainly within the specimen gauge length. In-plane fibre microbuckling is considered as the critical damage mechanism, which causes the catastrophic fracture, Fig.3a. Longitudinal splits and fibre/matrix debonding do not occur gradually but take place suddenly and concurrently with the final failure. The specimens generally fail along a $15^\circ(=\beta)$ line from the transverse axis, which is similar to the fracture line observed in [6].

Fig.3. A schematic representation of the microbuckling mode: a) in-plane, b) out-of-plane.

In the case of specimens tested at hot-wet conditions damage occurs in the middle of the specimen and grows almost perpendicular to the loading axis, Fig.3b. Subsequent examination by scanning electron microscopy revealed that the fibres underwent out-of-plane microbuckling.

The strain at which this failure mode initiates is reduced with increasing temperature and at 100° C is only 75% of the strain required to initiate in-plane microbuckling. Thus, any weakening of the matrix or fibre/matrix interface arising from elevated temperatures and environmental conditioning increases the probability of out-of-plane buckling of the fibres which results in degraded compressive strength.

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

Strength Data and Failure Modes

Compressive strength results for two multidirectional laminates with a 5 mm hole tested at various environmental conditions are summarised in Table 3. Strength values are based on the cross-sectional area of the test piece. It is clear that the compressive strength of the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_3]_s$ laminate is reduced by almost 38% when the specimen contains 1.42% moisture and is tested at 100°C-wet conditions (the room temperature unnotched strength is 810 MPa). The scatter in strength is less than 10% and all specimens failed from the hole in a direction

Table.3 Compressive strength results for T800/924C laminates with a 5mm hole.

Test Conditions °C	Notched Strength / MPa $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_3]_s$	Notched Strength / MPa $[(90_2, 0_2)_3]_s$
20-Dry	451.75	351.65
20-Wet	402.00	-
50-Dry	421.50	324.67
50-Wet	357.50	-
80-Dry	371.50	291.37
80-Wet	325.00	-
100-Wet	282.00	-

almost perpendicular to the loading axis. Penetrant-enhanced X-ray radiography and scanning electron microscopy reveal that failure is always by microbuckling of the 0° plies, and is accompanied by delamination between the off-axis and 0° layers, and by plastic deformation in the off-axis plies; similar observations were made in [8].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Untabbed straight-sided unidirectional and multidirectional specimens are tested following the procedures outlined in CRAG test methods [5]. The faces of the grip inserts of the test apparatus are spark-eroded to produce a surface finish of approximately 20 Ra. No damage to the surface plies is observed in specimens with uniform thickness and acceptable failure modes and location of failure are obtained. The diffusion coefficient and the equilibrium moisture content are measured and used with a computer program developed in [4] to estimate through

thickness moisture distribution. It is found that although Fickian diffusion does not exactly model the actual moisture absorption, it is sufficiently accurate for the cases examined.

The strength properties of specimens tested in hot-wet conditions are substantially reduced and the final failure always occurs due to out-of-plane fibre microbuckling. This is attributed to the reduction in matrix strength properties and weakening of the ply interface with increasing temperature and environmental conditioning. Thus, in compression the matrix and interface play a key role in providing side support to the fibres and consequently resistance to fibre buckling.

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